

Monte Carlo-Informed Analytical Tool for the Analysis of Noble Metals Decay Heat in the Molten Salt Reactor

Nicolò Iaselli^{1,*}, Stefano Lorenzi¹

¹Politecnico di Milano, Department of Energy, 34, Via La Masa, 20156 Milan, Italy

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ABSTRACT

Understanding the decay heat contribution of noble metals in Molten Salt Reactors is essential for assessing primary loop behavior during both steady operation and drain scenarios. This work develops a fast, Monte Carlo-informed analytical framework capable of tracking the full nuclide inventory across core, salt bulk and deposition regions, with possible applications to a commercial scale MSR. The model combines region-wise mass transfer correlations with a sparse transition operator that includes decay, convection, deposition and neutron-induced reactions. Reaction rates are obtained once from a high-fidelity Serpent 2 calculation, allowing the system of ODEs to be solved directly without repeated transport runs. The analytical tool is benchmarked against comparable Serpent 2 workflows for long-term evolution and reactor power modulation, achieving close agreement in both total decay heat and individual nuclide trends. Discrepancies remain small and physically interpretable, while computational cost is reduced from hours to seconds or minutes. This performance enables studies that would be impractical with Monte Carlo alone. Leveraging this capability, a frequency-domain analysis is performed to characterize the response of bulk and deposited nuclide inventories under low-frequency power modulation. The results reveal clear signatures tied to the temporal behavior of the deposited layer, providing a realistic pathway for estimating the decay heat from noble metals without repeated drain events. These findings support the design of an experimental campaign for the first demonstrative commercial reactor and illustrate the value of combining Monte Carlo results with lightweight analytical models for MSR system analysis.

Keywords: Molten Salt Reactor, Noble Metals, Particle Deposition, Digital Twin, Test Campaign

1. INTRODUCTION

Among the numerous solid Fission Product (FP) species, the noble metals are of particular interest due to their tendency to deposit on reactor surfaces, thus having a measurable impact on reactor performance and safety. Their behavior, recognized as critical since the conceptual phase of the first Molten Salt Reactor (MSR) designs, was extensively documented during the Molten Salt Reactor Experiment (MSRE) [1]. In parallel, a 0-dimensional analytical model—including source, decay, removal and deposition terms—was developed to track noble-metal migration along the primary loop [2]. This formulation already captured the essential physics behind migration and accumulation but relied on a strongly reduced nuclide set, mainly due to the computational constraints of that time. More recent efforts have expanded the treatment of fission product classes and implemented transport equations in system codes such as SPECTRA, although, as noted in [3], “the main observations from the MSRE operation [...] are basis for the fission product modeling assumptions.” This highlights the persistent need to experimentally validate both the modeling assumptions and the impact of noble metal decay heat on commercial reactor design. This aspect becomes especially relevant when considering safety-related drain scenarios: once the fuel salt is discharged, the noble metal deposits remain without active cooling, and their radioactive decay can generate localized overheating, potentially compromising primary-loop

*nicolo.iaselli@polimi.it

structural integrity before any mitigation is possible. A reliable predictive tool is therefore essential to support both preliminary design decisions and the planning of targeted experimental investigations.

This work presents a Monte Carlo-informed analytical tool developed specifically to address this need. The method combines high-fidelity Serpent 2 reaction rate data with a sparse, fully deterministic ODE formulation that can track the full nuclide inventory across the core, bulk flow, and deposition regions with a very small computational footprint. Once the transmutation operator is extracted, the model runs in seconds while still reproducing the key trends observed in detailed Serpent simulations, both in steady conditions and under power modulation. Compared to earlier models, it handles a much larger set of nuclides, retains the underlying neutron-induced transmutation behavior, and avoids the limitations of repeated Monte Carlo runs. These features make the tool well suited to support a tailored experimental campaign for the Thorcon 500 MSR [4], where understanding how decay heat responds to low-frequency power perturbations is central to interpreting future measurements and constraining the impact of noble metals deposition in a commercial system.

2. MULTIPHYSICS SIMULATION FRAMEWORK

2.1. Analytical Modeling of the Nuclide Inventory

To describe the time evolution of the nuclide inventory across the different regions of the primary loop, the analytical model treats each node as a lumped control volume and expresses all interactions through a linear system of ODEs. The various physical processes acting on each nuclide—decay, neutron-induced reactions, convection, and deposition—are incorporated through dedicated operator terms, collected according to whether they are time-dependent or not. This leads to a compact formulation in which the total inventory evolves according to:

$$\frac{d\mathbf{N}(t)}{dt} = [\mathbf{M}_{tr} + \mathbf{M}_{nr}(t)] \cdot \mathbf{N}(t) + \dot{\mathbf{S}}_{ext}(t) \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{M}_{tr} is the overall transition matrix, $\mathbf{M}_{nr}(t)$ is the neutron-induced transmutation matrix, and $\dot{\mathbf{S}}_{ext}$ is the sum of all the possible sources that are external to the node.

Starting from \mathbf{M}_{tr} , this is an $n \times n$ matrix where n is the number of nuclides being modeled, and includes only the contributions that are—either physically or by approximation—invariant with time. The values are obtained as the algebraic sum of the following terms:

- the decay matrix \mathbf{M}_{dec} , built with negative diagonal terms acting as a sink for parent nuclides and positive branching ratio-weighted decay rates for the respective daughter(s). This is populated using data extracted from *endf* files contained in the ENDF/B-VIII.0 nuclear library [5].
- the convective outflow matrix $\mathbf{M}_{c,out}$, which, under the assumption of perfectly mixed fuel salt nuclide inventory, is fully diagonal with the same transfer rate for all species.
- and the deposition matrix \mathbf{M}_{dep} , containing the transfer rates calculated in Section 2.2.

The choice of implementing outflow convection and deposition through diagonal matrices, instead of n -dimensional vectors, leads to the simplicity of Equation (1), where different types of contributions can be grouped together in the standard homogeneous/inhomogeneous terms formulation. The resulting transition matrix is therefore populated only very close to the diagonal and features less than 0.06% non-zero elements, meaning that it is characterized by extreme sparsity.

On the other hand, the neutron-induced transmutation matrix $\mathbf{M}_{nr}(t)$ is built by extracting reaction rates (in s^{-1}) from the reference Monte Carlo burnup runs. In practice, given that not all the nuclides worth tracking are present simultaneously at a given time—at least not in sufficient quantity to trust the simulation tallies—the rates are selected between all runs to have the smallest statistical error. It is worth noting that an alternative route would be to extract only the neutron spectrum and calculate the rates for each nuclide, and for each possible reaction, as the sum of the spectrum-weighted reac-

tion cross section. Albeit justified by the satisfactory results that will be presented, the approximation of constant reaction rates was easily motivated, since the flux-weighted inverse neutron speed $\langle 1/v \rangle$ remains essentially constant over burnup, with a relative standard deviation—thus including Monte Carlo statistical uncertainty—of only 0.3%. This means that the neutron-induced transmutation matrix can be factorized as:

$$\mathbf{M}_{nr}(t) = \mathbf{M}_{nr|P_{ref}} \frac{P(t)}{P_{ref}} \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{M}_{nr|P_{ref}}$ is a constant matrix built at a reference reactor power P_{ref} , and $P(t)$ is the time-dependent reactor thermal output. It is important to highlight how convective inflow and outflow for each node are treated separately because otherwise the net contribution would always be identically zero for mass conservation in a closed loop. As mentioned above, the outflow term is implemented proportionally to the inventory of a given node, with the same quantity being added as inflow to the following node:

$$\dot{S}_{c,in,i+1}(t) = \mathbf{M}_{c,out} \cdot \mathbf{N}_i(t) \quad (3)$$

This effectively acts as a coupling term between all elements of the framework, reflecting the physical behavior of the MSR primary loop. This ensures a more accurate modeling of the behavior of bulk decay heat along the primary loop during reactor modulation and also, with a minor impact, in steady state conditions. Finally, depending on the node type, Equation (1) is implemented as:

$$\frac{d\mathbf{N}(t)}{dt} = \left[\left(\mathbf{M}_{dec} + \mathbf{M}_{dep} + \mathbf{M}_{c,out} \right) + \mathbf{M}_{nr}(t) \right] \cdot \mathbf{N}(t) + \dot{S}_{c,in}(t) + \dot{S}_{repr}(t) \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{d\mathbf{N}(t)}{dt} = \left(\mathbf{M}_{dec} - \mathbf{M}_{dep} + \mathbf{M}_{c,out} \right) \cdot \mathbf{N}(t) + \dot{S}_{c,in}(t) + \dot{S}_{repr}(t) \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{d\mathbf{N}(t)}{dt} = \left(\mathbf{M}_{dec} + \mathbf{M}_{dep} \right) \cdot \mathbf{N}(t) \quad (6)$$

where Equation (4) is valid for the core node, Equation (5) holds for salt bulk nodes, and Equation (6) for any deposition node.

This analytical tool advances the multiphysics system by directly integrating the ODEs with the *scipy solve_ivp* tool, using the assembled matrix operator and external source terms. Given an initial inventory and a prescribed time grid, the solver returns the nuclide vector at each evaluation point without any chain reconstruction or approximations (other than the integrator tolerances). This provides a fully deterministic time evolution that can be post-processed to compute decay heat or any other aggregate quantity.

2.2. Noble Metals Modeling

This work introduces a correlation-based 0-dimensional framework for modeling noble metal migration in MSRs. In this formulation, no spatial gradients are resolved along the circuit, as the focus is placed on the average behavior of the flow within each component or pipe segment. This approach, adopted instead of a CFD-based modeling [6], facilitates integration into a digital twin environment, while also providing value for outlining tailored experimental campaigns.

Each region of the primary loop is treated as a lumped control volume with an equivalent pipe flow and characteristic thermo-hydraulic conditions. Under these assumptions, the Sherwood number, which

represents the ratio between convective and diffusive mass transfer, can be determined from the following relationships:

$$Sh_x = 1.86 \cdot Re^{0.33} \cdot Sc^{0.33} \cdot \left(\frac{d_h}{x}\right)^{0.33} \quad (\text{Re} < 1e3) \quad (7)$$

$$Sh = 0.023 \cdot Re^{0.8} \cdot Sc^{0.4} \quad (\text{Re} > 1e4, \text{ turbulent forced convection}) \quad (8)$$

where Re is the Reynolds number, Sc the Schmidt number, d_h the hydraulic diameter, and x the distance from the flow entrance. These expressions stem from the Sieder–Tate and Dittus–Boelter heat transfer correlations respectively, adapted through the Chilton–Colburn analogy [7]. The corresponding mass transfer coefficient follows directly as:

$$mtc = \frac{Sh \cdot D_L}{d_h} \quad (9)$$

where D_L (in m^2/s) denotes the diffusivity of noble metals in FLiBe salt [2]. Despite the likelihood of species and isotope-dependent variations, this value—derived from MSRE data—remains the most credible experimental reference available. To date, no study has reported specific diffusivities for different particle sizes or chemical forms in molten salt conditions, highlighting the need for targeted measurements to strengthen predictive models of noble metal transport.

The variation in time of a given nuclide concentration in a salt bulk node due to deposition is therefore:

$$\frac{dC}{dt} = mtc \cdot \frac{A_s}{V} \cdot (C_b - C_s) \quad (10)$$

where V is the control volume, A_s is the surface area available for deposition, and C_b and C_s represent bulk and surface concentrations, respectively. Under the assumption that reactor surfaces behave as infinite sinks, the surface concentration is effectively zero, and deposition is governed solely by the bulk concentration. Under this conservative assumption, noble metal particles will continue to accumulate on surfaces over the course of reactor operation. Finally, the deposition rate (or velocity) is extracted as $\lambda = mtc \cdot A_s/V$ (in s^{-1}), which is the most convenient deposition quantity to be used for both the Serpent-based and analytical approach, where it is used to build the M_{dep} matrix.

The model will be used assuming constant primary flow rate under any conditions. This is of course not the case when looking at the real plant behavior, but it is definitely achievable in pre-licensing test scenarios. As previously highlighted, the flow regime has a strong impact on the depositional effects and frequent reactor power adjustments would therefore lead to different results. For the scope of this work, this dependency was removed to focus on the development of the analytical model itself and its application to the investigation of the experimental campaign. Nevertheless, it will be clear from the following discussion that the implementation of a time-varying convective term is certainly within the capabilities of this simulation framework.

2.3. Serpent-Based Approach

This approach relies almost entirely on the Serpent 2 Monte Carlo code, capable of criticality and burnup calculations, and also equipped with a routine for online fuel reprocessing. This last feature can be exploited to model material flows through 0-dimensional components and onto depositional nodes, therefore serving as the core of the multiphysics simulation framework. The implementation is based on the so-called reprocessing constant λ , which prescribes the rate of mass transfer from material i to material j as:

$$\dot{m}_{i \rightarrow j} = \lambda_{i \rightarrow j} \cdot \rho_i \cdot V_i \quad (11)$$

This formulation can be easily applied to both convective and deposition transfer rates. The depletion algorithm and system advancement considering these features is therefore handled entirely within the

standard burnup workflow. Such a model has been verified in previous endeavors against MSRE data, with satisfactory results [8], and will therefore serve as a reference for the present work.

3. PERFORMANCE AND ACCURACY BENCHMARK

The computational performance and accuracy of the presented analytical model have been assessed against simulations run entirely within the Serpent 2 workflow presented in Section 2.3. Two benchmarks were performed and are presented following the order of development. The first one is dedicated to long-term system evolution under constant reactor power, highlighting the quality of both bulk and deposited decay heat predictions. The second one instead focuses on the behavior related to reactor power modulation, which is particularly valuable in the context of experimental applications, as discussed in Section 4.

3.1. Long-term system evolution

The system is initialized with a fresh fuel salt composition, including the FLiBe mixture ($\text{LiF} - \text{BeF}_2 - \text{ZrF}_4 - \text{UF}_4$), the required uranium enrichment, and metallic impurities from salt fabrication and storage [9]. The benchmark adopts a homogeneous salt and graphite core with the correct fuel-to-moderator ratio, suitable albedo boundary conditions, and a single deposition node; additional primary-loop regions are omitted to focus on the core physics reproduced by the analytical model (i.e., FPs behavior). On the reprocessing side, only the off-gas line is modeled, preserving the removal of gaseous nuclides typical of MSR systems. Makeup fertile addition—necessary for long-term operation at nominal power—would require a dedicated reactivity-control algorithm, which lies outside the scope of this work. Instead, the Serpent case is run at low power (1 kW) and nominal deposition rates, avoiding significant depletion of both ^{235}U and ^{238}U . This simplified scenario is justified by the negligible change in the neutron spectrum even at nominal power, despite higher relative concentrations of fission and transmutation products. The Serpent reference simulation uses 250 active cycles with a population of 1000 neutrons per cycle. Burnup is divided into 100 logarithmically spaced steps and advanced through a linear extrapolation–corrector scheme; depletion is handled with the 14th-order CRAM solver and ENDF/B-VIII.0 nuclear data. From this output, the reaction rates are extracted and used to assemble $M_{nr|Pref}$, following the approach described in Section 2.1, and the analytical model is run under the same conditions. The resulting differences in total decay heat remain small: as shown in Figure 1a, the bulk node exhibits a clearer mismatch during the first couple of minutes, after which the discrepancy steadily decreases towards zero, while the deposition node remains within a $\pm 0.3\%$ band. During modulation, this residual steady-state discrepancy is expected to combine with the contribution of short-lived nuclides.

The true value of this analytical approach, however, lies in its execution speed and versatility. Once that a specific reactor core design is selected for analysis, a single Serpent run can be performed to build the neutron-induced transmutation operator and then the analytical model can be independently executed thereafter. The relatively high-statistics Monte Carlo run in this case took 24.5 minutes for overall completion on a high-end laptop, against 4 seconds for the analytical approach. This huge difference evidently lies in the time it takes Serpent to load and process cross section data and to transport the prescribed neutron generations for each of the burnup steps, with rapidly diminishing returns on the accuracy concerning the applications of this work.

3.2. Reactor power modulation

A second benchmark is performed to evaluate the analytical model under reactor power modulation. The reference simulation uses parameters similar to those reported in Section 3.1, but with 600 transport cycles to keep the overall runtime and discretization reasonable for this analysis. A full simulation at a given modulation frequency takes about 6 hours, with a large fraction of the time spent repeatedly loading and unloading cross sections from system RAM. In practice, a more reasonable runtime for

(a) Relative discrepancy on total decay heat between the analytical model and Serpent results.

(b) Contribution of individual nuclides to the discrepancy at the end of the simulation.

Figure 1. Benchmark accuracy results concerning long-term system evolution.

this benchmark would be around 2 hours—still much higher than the roughly 50 seconds required by the analytical tool. Results are shown in Figure 2, where the modulation-dependent discrepancy is clearly visible for each case. It is also worth noting that, in this setup, the analytical tool might actually outperform the Serpent workflow thanks to its finer time resolution and more robust implementation. A dedicated sensitivity study on the Monte Carlo parameters would be needed to confirm or refute this hypothesis, and could be explored in future work.

Figure 2. Benchmark results for reactor modulation. The upper plot illustrates bulk decay heat discrepancy for different modulation periods, and the lower plot shows the corresponding reactor power waveform.

4. SYSTEM RESPONSE IN THE FREQUENCY DOMAIN

4.1. Reactor Modulation Analysis

Once the validity of the analytical model is assessed, it is possible to exploit the significant increase in execution speed to perform analysis that would otherwise be computationally impractical. Taking into consideration the experimental campaign foreseen for a commercial reactor such as the Thorcon 500, the possibility of measuring the decay heat from deposited noble metals without repeated drain events is highly valuable. The crucial aspect is that the noble metals deposit exhibits a significantly larger effective decay constant with respect to the bulk, meaning that a frequency analysis can help estimate the decay heat contribution. This partitioning effect of the deposition can be seen from Figure 3a and Figure 3b. First, low modulation frequencies are required to obtain valuable insights, since above 10^{-3} Hz there is no variation with respect to the deposition velocity. In particular, the gain of the decay heat signal, calculated as the ratio between amplitudes of decay heat and reactor power, is smaller when depositional effects are more relevant. This is physically sound since the overall nuclide inventory in the bulk is smaller as a consequence of the deposition sink. On the other hand, the phase shift is less prominent at larger deposition rates because the remaining nuclides are more prone to input following (i.e., smaller characteristic time).

Figure 3. Frequency-domain system response (salt bulk decay heat) as a function of modulation frequency and deposition rate.

4.2. Considerations on the Experimental Strategy

The relevance of these results is that the behavior of the first demonstrative Thorcon reactor can be compared with the expected one from the frequency analysis to find a reasonable range for the decay heat from deposited noble metals. Attempting to obtain very accurate knowledge of the amount and precise distribution of the deposit layer would likely be very challenging, with little to no benefit since there are other significant sources of uncertainty impacting on the final design and mitigating actions. The success of an experimental campaign that follows this approach is based on different requirements. First, the total nuclide inventory in the primary loop can be known with a fair accuracy. This is not too far from reality since high-fidelity Monte Carlo and deterministic transport simulations can reconstruct a realistic neutron flux in both energy and time. Fission yields and decay chains are experimentally well characterized, while the neutron-induced reaction rates might suffer from high uncertainty regions in

some cross section datasets. Moreover, experimental validation of these aspects on the very reactor could further improve accuracy. Another requirement is that a suitable decay heat measurement setup can be realized for the specific needs of this analysis, especially since the impact of noble metals decay heat is easily overshadowed by inherent primary loop dynamics and by the thermal reactor power itself. Further advancements on these aspects would be of extreme value for a commercial reactor such as the Thorcon 500 MSR.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The presented work shows that a compact analytical framework can accurately reproduce the decay heat behavior of both salt bulk and noble metal deposits in an MSR while operating orders of magnitude faster than a full Monte Carlo workflow. By extracting a single high-quality transmutation operator from Serpent and embedding it into a sparse ODE solver, the model captures both long-term evolution and modulation-driven dynamics with small, physically interpretable discrepancies. This speedup makes it possible to explore scenarios, such as frequency-response analysis of deposited versus bulk nuclides, that would be prohibitively expensive with traditional burnup calculations. The frequency-domain results highlight clear signatures linked to the effective decay constants of the deposit layer, suggesting a practical path for interpreting power modulation experiments at low frequencies. Overall, the study demonstrates that this approach can guide the design of a realistic experimental campaign while offering a scalable tool for future system-level analyses of MSR behavior.

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